

Zero PM

Zero pollution of Persistent, Mobile substances

Grant Agreement No. 101036756

Regulatory watch - 2025

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101036756.

Summary

This report compiles all the issues of ZeroPM's monthly Regulatory watch for 2025.

Contents

1	Regulatory watch – January 2025	4
2	Regulatory watch – February 2025	6
3	Regulatory watch – March 2025	7
4	Regulatory watch – April 2025	10
5	Regulatory watch – May 2025	12
6	Regulatory watch – June 2025	15
7	Regulatory watch – July 2025	18
8	Regulatory watch – August 2025	21
9	Regulatory watch – September 2025	23
10	Regulatory watch – October 2025	25
11	Regulatory watch – November 2025	27
12	Regulatory watch – December 2025	30

1 Regulatory watch – January 2025

Sweden calls for generic bans for most harmful substances in consumer products in REACH revision

At the Environment Council of 17 December, Sweden, supported by Denmark, Finland and Luxembourg, presented an [information note](#) calling for introducing generic bans for the most harmful substances (e.g. carcinogens, endocrine disruptors) in consumer products through the revision of the REACH Regulation, announced for 2025. According to the four Member States, the adoption of generic bans would be ‘simpler, more predictable and faster’ than the current restriction requirements and would minimise the presence of harmful chemicals in recycled materials. No other Member State endorsed the information note during the Council meeting, although some expressed support for the revision of REACH for its general objectives of improving the protection of human health and the environment. The Netherlands indicated they have a different view on generic risk management than that proposed in the information note, as generic bans ‘could have disproportionate effects’ and should only be used after identifying risks of exposure to substances of very high concern’.

MEPs calls for further action to address drinking water contamination with PFAS

During a [plenary debate in the European Parliament](#) on the right to clean drinking water in the EU, several MEPs raised concerns about PFAS pollution in EU drinking water and called for further action to tackle pollution at source, including rapidly adopting a broad PFAS restriction (not only in consumer products, but also professional products), introducing monitoring requirements and quality standards for PFAS in surface water (as proposed in ongoing revision of the EQS Directive), banning the use of PFAS pesticides, taking additional measures to ensure the application of the polluter pays principle, and support local authorities and water suppliers in financing advanced water treatment. Executive Vice-President for Cohesion and Reforms Raffaele Fitto replied that the Commission ‘has launched a study to evaluate the technical and economic feasibility of treatment techniques for removing PFAS from drinking water’ and ‘will consider what steps might need to be taken to further protect human health through the Drinking Water Directive’. Additionally, the Commission will ‘make sure that that these topics are properly addressed in the water resilience strategy’, announced as a Commission priority.

Soil monitoring, One Substance - One Assessment package and priority substances in water on Polish presidency’s table

Poland took over the presidency of the Council of the European Union from Hungary on 1 January 2025 and will hold it until June. The [programme of the Polish presidency](#) announces the continuation of negotiations with the European Parliament on the Soil Monitoring Directive, as no deal could be reached between the two institutions in December. The presidency also indicates it will initiate negotiations with the European Parliament on the One Substance - One Assessment package. The programme finally mentions the continuation and possible finalisation of the negotiations on the amendments to the Directives on priority substances in water (Water Framework Directive, Groundwater Directive, Environmental Quality Standards Directive).

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

No deadline this month!

2 Regulatory watch – February 2025

Targeted REACH revision on the Commission’s agenda for Q4 2025

The Commission released its [2025 work programme](#) on 12 February. The work programme lists the new initiatives (including legislative and non-legislative initiatives), pending files and planned withdrawals for this year. In the wake of the [Competitiveness compass](#), published on 29 January, over half of the 45 new initiatives aim to support EU’s competitiveness (12 initiatives) and simplify the regulatory environment (11 initiatives). The targeted revision of the REACH Regulation, which is also considered as a simplification initiative, is planned for the end of the year (Q4 2025). Among non-legislative initiatives, the European Water Resilience Strategy is planned for Q2 2025.

ENVI Committee’s draft report stresses importance of addressing water pollution to achieve water resilience

The Environment Committee’s rapporteur for the European Parliament’s own initiative report on the European Water Resilience Strategy issued its [draft report](#) on 29 January. The report states that ‘addressing pollution is equally essential to achieving water resilience’ as is water efficiency. The report calls for better implementation and enforcement of the current EU water policy framework, calls on the Commission to ‘establish comprehensive EU-wide quality standards for PFAS totals in groundwater and surface water’, stresses the need to address pollution from pharmaceuticals and other emerging pollutants and to better monitor pesticide residues in water. The report also asks the Commission to create a dedicated fund for water resilience in the upcoming multi-annual financial framework and calls for a wider application of the cost recovery principle. The draft report will be discussed in the ENVI Committee next month and is expected to be adopted early April 2025.

Call for evidence on the European Water Resilience Strategy

The Commission has launched a [call for evidence](#) to inform the upcoming European Water Resilience Strategy on 4 February. As previously announced, the strategy focuses on restoring and protection the broken water cycle, ensuring clean and affordable water and sanitation for all and promoting a competitive EU water industry and a clean, water-wise and circular economy. The Strategy will address five action areas: governance and implementation, infrastructure, finance and investments, security, and industry, innovation and education. The Strategy will take the form of a Communication, expected to be published in Q2 2025. In addition to the Call for Evidence, a [stakeholder consultation event](#) will be held on 6 March in Brussels.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to provide feedback to the call for evidence on the European Water Resilience Strategy: **4 March 2025.**

3 Regulatory watch – March 2025

New surface water watchlist requires Member States to monitor triazoles, 6PPD-quinone and TFA precursor Fluoxetine in surface waters in the next years

The Commission adopted the [fifth watchlist of substances in surface waters](#) suspected of posing a risk to the environment and human health on 28 February. The surface watchlist mechanism was established in 2013 to improve the available information on substances of concern. Member States have to monitor the substances on the list at least once per year for up to four years. The new watchlist contains twelve chemicals or groups of chemicals, some of which are new on the list, some of which were included in the previous watchlist but for which the Commission considered that insufficient high-quality monitoring data have so far been obtained. The list includes several PMT/vPvM substances or precursors of PMT/vPvM substances:

- ▼ 6PPD-quinone (CAS no. 2754428-18-5) (new on the watchlist)
- ▼ 10 azole fungicides, including in particular bromuconazole (CAS no. 116255-48-2), climbazole (CAS no. 38083-17-9), difenoconazole (CAS no. 119446-68-3), mefentrifluconazole (CAS no. 1417782-03-6), and triticonazole (CAS no. 131983-72-7) (all new on the watchlist)
- ▼ TFA precursor Fluoxetine (CAS no. 54910-89-3) (new on the watchlist)
- ▼ UV blocker Benzophenone-3 (CAS no. 131-57-7) (from previous watchlist)

The data will help the Commission to determine whether the substances pose a widespread risk and should be considered for inclusion in the list of priority substances under the Water Framework Directive (i.e. substances for which an EQS should be determined).

ENVI Committee includes information on substances in articles and alternatives to substances of concern in common chemicals data platform and expands ECHA's tasks to investigate emerging chemical risks

The European Parliament's ENVI Committee adopted its report on the one substance, one assessment package on 18 February. The [report on the common data platform](#) proposes to include in the platform a database of information on substances in articles and a database of information on alternatives to substances of concern.

The ENVI Committee has added the possibility for researchers to submit to ECHA publicly available research data on chemicals related to an entry in the common data platform. If ECHA assesses that the data submitted fulfils the quality and reporting requirements, defined by a Commission guidance, it must then be hosted on the common data platform. This new provision aims to increase the uptake of independent research studies, often given comparatively low weight as evidence in hazard and risk assessment of chemicals.

Based on the annual reports on early warning signals that ECHA is tasked with, the ENVI Committee has adopted an amendment requiring the Commission and national authorities to 'undertake regulatory, policy or enforcement actions' on the signals within

six months of the presentation of the report, or to ‘justify if they decide not to proceed with any action’.

ENVI Committee has also extended the possibilities for ECHA to commission scientific studies to investigate further emerging chemical risks identified through the early warning system and to conduct Union-wide data sampling survey of human biomonitoring in collaboration with Member states. The report also stipulates that ECHA can request from a business operator a sample of substance that is indispensable to perform the scientific study. Amendments from the ENVI Committee also require that ECHA, in cooperation with EFSA, commissions every five years an EU-wide human biomonitoring study that covers all EU member states and propose the creation of a 'chemicals exposure index' for each region in the EU, to provide an overview of the population's exposure to chemical substances.

Finally, the Committee specifies that the platform must be accessible to authorities and the public free of charge, establishes a minimum list of datasets that should be available on the date the platform is released, and shortens the timeframe for making available all datasets to 8 years (instead of 10 years). The report will be adopted in plenary the week of 31 March.

France adopts PFAS ban in textiles, cosmetics and ski waxes

The [draft law to protect the public from the risks associated with PFAS](#) was adopted by the French Parliament on 20 February 2025. The law bans, from 1 January 2026, the manufacturing, placing on the market, import and export of cosmetic products, waxes, clothing, shoes and waterproofing agents containing PFAS (with the exception of certain protective clothing and footwear for professional uses, notably for defence and civil protection). The law bans, from 1 January 2030, the manufacturing, placing on the market, import and export of all textiles containing PFAS (with some exceptions for essential uses, the list of which will be adopted through implementing acts). These bans will however not apply to products containing PFAS in concentrations less than or equal to a residual value that will be defined by an implementing act. The ban in food contact materials, initially included in the proposal, was removed, since the adoption of amendment to the Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation banning the placing on the market of food contact packaging containing PFAS in the EU.

The law also introduces a number of provisions related to PFAS in drinking water, including;

- ▼ An obligation for regional health authorities to control a wider list of PFAS in drinking water than required the Drinking water Directive. In the [parliamentary debates](#), the rapporteur mentioned in particular TFA.
- ▼ A requirement to establish and make publicly available a map, to be updated annually, of all the sites that have emitted or are emitting PFAS into the environment, including, where possible, quantitative measurements of emissions.
- ▼ A requirement for the Government to propose updated health standards for PFAS in water intended for human consumption within a year of the adoption of the law

- ▼ A requirement for the government to adopt a national action plan for the gradual reduction of industrial emissions of PFAS in water, with the aim of eliminating these discharges within 5 years of the adoption of the law
- ▼ A requirement for the government to put forward an action plan for financing the decontamination of drinking water within a year of the adoption of the law
- ▼ A fee based on PFAS discharges into water payable by certain industrial installations to the water agencies (similar to what already exists in France for other pollutants like phosphorus, nitrites or nitrates). The fee (€100 per 100 grams) and will be used to finance drinking water filtration systems. The list of substances concerned by the fee will be adopted by an implementing act.
- ▼ A requirement for the regional health agencies to publish annual regional reports on the monitoring of PFAS in drinking water, particularly bottled water, and for the Health Minister to publish an annual national report on the quality of drinking water in France with regard to PFAS.

Zero Pollution Monitoring and Outlook report shows stronger EU action is needed to achieve 2030 pollution reduction targets

The Commission and the European Environment Agency published on 3 March the [second Zero Pollution Monitoring and Outlook report](#). The report provides an overview of the EU's work and progress to meet the 2030 zero pollution targets. Although the report notes progress towards some of the [pollution reduction targets](#) (marine litter, pesticides and antimicrobials), the report concludes that much stronger action is necessary in the EU to achieve its 2030 pollution reduction targets.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to provide feedback to the [call for evidence](#) on the European Water Resilience Strategy: **4 March 2025**.
- ▼ Deadline to provide feedback to the [call for evidence](#) on the evaluation of the Cosmetic Products Regulation: **21 March 2025**.

4 Regulatory watch – April 2025

Member States back non-renewal of approval of flufenacet

At the meeting of the standing committee of plants, animals, food and feed (SCoPAFF) on 11-12 March 2025, Member States [voted in favour](#) of the draft Regulation concerning the non-renewal of the approval of the active substance flufenacet. The [draft Regulation](#) highlights the ‘potential for the flufenacet metabolite trifluoroacetic acid (‘TFA’) to contaminate groundwater at levels that significantly exceed the statutory limit of 0.1 µg/l, provided for in the Groundwater Directive’.

During the same meeting, Member States discussed but did not vote on the draft Regulation concerning the non-renewal of the approval of the active substance flutolanil. The [Draft Renewal report](#) discussed at the meeting indicates that ‘the lack of knowledge on the level of TFA residues in rotational crops represents a significant uncertainty in the consumer risk assessment and a potential risk for groundwater’ and concludes that the approval of flutolanil should not be renewed.

2025-2027 CoRAP update includes five new suspected PMT/vPvM

The [Community rolling action plan \(CoRAP\) update for the years 2025-2027](#), published on 25 March, lists 28 substances for evaluation by 8 Member State Competent Authorities, including 13 new substances compared to the previous CoRAP. Among the new substances, five are suspected PMT/vPvM, to be evaluated by Spanish authorities in 2026:

- ▼ A mixture of branched and linear C7-C9 alkyl 3-[3-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-5-(1,1-dimethylethyl)-4-hydroxyphenyl]propionates
- ▼ A mixture of: a-3-(3-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-5-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)propionyl-?-hydroxypoly(oxyethylene); a-3-(3-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-5-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)propionyl-?-3-(3-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-5-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)propionyloxypoly(oxyethylene)
- ▼ Methyl 3-[3-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-4-hydroxy-5-(2-methyl-2-propanyl)phenyl]propanoate
- ▼ Reaction mass of Octyl-3-[3-tert-butyl-4-hydroxy-5-(5-chloro-2H-benzotriazole-2-yl)phenyl]propionate and 2-Ethylhexyl-3-[3-tert-butyl-4-hydroxy-5-(5-chloro-2H-benzotriazole-2-yl)phenyl]propionate
- ▼ Di-substituted tert-alkyl 3-[3-(2H-benzotriazol-2-yl)-5-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl]propanoate

Norway submits classification and labelling (CLH) intentions for two PMT/vPvM

On 25 March, Norway submitted classification and labelling (CLH) intentions for the classification of Dimethylsilanediol (CAS No. 1066-42-8) and 1,1,2,2,3,3,4,4,4-nonafluorobutane-1-sulphonic acid (CAS No. 375-73-5) as PMT and vPvM.

Parliament adopts position on the One substance, one assessment package

The European Parliament has adopted in plenary session on 1 April 2025 its [amendments on the proposal for a regulation establishing a common data platform on chemicals](#) and

[other texts](#) of the one substance, one assessment package – which replicate the ENVI Committee reports adopted in February. Following this vote, interinstitutional negotiations will likely start in the coming weeks and may be concluded during the Polish Presidency of the Council.

Cosmetic and pharmaceutical industries challenge UWWTD's EPR system before CJEU

The Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive, adopted in October 2024, establishes an extended producer responsibility scheme in which producers of pharmaceuticals and cosmetics would contribute a minimum of 80% of the costs of quaternary treatment. [Cosmetics Europe](#) and the [European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations](#) have announced in March 2025 having filed legal actions with the EU General Court to seek clarity on the rationale to include only two sectors in the EPR system bearing alone the costs of quaternary treatment while other sectors contribute to wastewater pollution. Both organisations ask for costs to be fairly distributed across sectors according to the share of pollution they represent.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to provide feedback on the [Application for the renewal of approval of the active substance Tau-fluvalinate](#) (EFSA): **13 April 2025**.
- ▼ Deadline to provide feedback on EFSA's [Draft guidance on the use of read-across for chemical safety assessment in food and feed](#): **21 April 2025**.
- ▼ Deadline to provide feedback on the [Assessment Report on the active substance tebuconazole](#) (EFSA): **28 April 2025**.
- ▼ Deadline to provide feedback to the [Call for evidence](#) and respond to the [public consultation](#) on the evaluation of the Good Laboratory Practices Directives: **6 June 2025**.

5 Regulatory watch – May 2025

Council and Parliament reached provisional agreement on Soil Monitoring Directive

On 10 April, the Council and the Parliament reached a provisional agreement on the Soil Monitoring Directive. The Directive establishes a monitoring framework to assess soil health and address contaminated sites. According to the [Council press release](#), ‘first steps towards monitoring of PFAS and pesticides were agreed by the co-legislators’. The text of the agreement is not yet publicly available. More details will be provided in the next regulatory watch editions.

Council and Parliament reached provisional agreement on Toy Safety Regulation

On 10 April, the Council and the European Parliament reached a provisional agreement on the Toy Safety Regulation. According to the [Council press release](#), the agreement ‘introduces a limited ban on the intentional use of PFAS in toys (with exemptions for toy components necessary for electronic or electric functions of the toy where the substance or mixture is fully inaccessible to children)’. The text of the agreement is not yet publicly available. More details will be provided in the next regulatory watch editions.

Member States back restriction of PFAS in firefighting foams

During the meeting of the REACH Committee on 29 April 2025, nearly all Member States (26 out of 27) [voted in favour](#) of the [draft regulation](#) introducing a restriction of PFAS in firefighting foams. The restriction sets a maximum concentration of 1 mg/L for the sum of all PFAS in firefighting foams. The restriction provides a ten-year transition period for firefighting foams used in installations belonging to the offshore oil and gas industry, military vessels, civilian ships, industrial sites covered by the Seveso Directive. Transitional periods are also provided for the use of firefighting foams containing PFAS above the set threshold in public fire services (18 months) and portable fire extinguishers (31 December 2030). The restriction also sets out labelling requirements applicable to fighting foams containing PFAS above the set threshold and to the stock of not-utilised firefighting foams and PFAS-containing waste.

European Parliament adopts its resolution on the European Water Resilience Strategy Report

On 7 May, the European Parliament adopted in plenary session its [resolution on the European Water Resilience Strategy](#). The final resolution incorporates part of the ENVI Committee's draft report on water pollution, calling on the Commission to establish a ‘comprehensive EU-wide quality standards for PFAS in groundwater and surface water’, to address ‘pollution from pharmaceuticals, bisphenols and other emerging pollutants’ and to increase ‘monitoring of pesticide residues in water bodies and enforcement of pesticide application regulations’. The final resolution contains a new paragraph that ‘calls on the Commission to propose updated limits on PFAS in drinking water, taking into account the latest scientific knowledge’.

The Parliament also introduced a new paragraph concerning sewage sludge, recognising the importance of treated sludge as a source of fertiliser and emphasising ‘the importance

of preventing PFAS, heavy metals, microplastics and other harmful substances from entering sewer networks in order to enable the safe and sustainable use of high-quality sewage sludge in agriculture’.

Another new element of the resolution is the addition of a paragraph related to the universal PFAS restriction, stressing that ‘essential uses of PFAS in critical sectors’, such as medical devices, pharmaceuticals or critical for the energy transition, ‘are not endangered’, and calling on the Commission to phase out PFAS in consumer goods, but allowing their use ‘where there are no safe alternatives’. An exchange of views between the ENVI Committee and the Commission on EU actions related to PFAS on 15 April 2025 had shown divergences between political groups, some of them (EPP and ECR) calling to avoid a ‘blanket ban’.

Finally, the European Parliament introduced a new paragraph on the EPR system under the revised Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive, expressing concerns regarding the impact of the EPR system on the pharmaceutical sector and in particular on the ‘availability and affordability’ of medicines, and calling on the Commission to reassess the impact on this sector.

Commission tightens PFOS limits in POPs Regulation

On 14 April 2025, the Commission adopted a [draft delegated regulation](#) amending the Persistent Organic Pollutant (POP) Regulation regarding PFOS. The draft regulation introduces an Unintentional Trace Contaminant (UTC) limit value for PFOS and its salts of 0,025 mg/kg (in line with the one for PFOA). It reduces the UTC limit value for PFOS-related compounds in substances, mixtures and articles to 1 mg/kg (bringing it in line with the one for PFOA). Both limits will apply from 3 December 2025. The regulation also removes the specific exemption for the use of PFOS as mist suppressant for non-decorative hard-chromium plating.

On 5 May, the Commission also adopted the [amendment to the POP Regulation](#) extending the the expiry date of the specific exemption for the use for fire-fighting foams (already installed in systems) containing PFOA, its salts and PFOA related substances until 3 December 2025.

ECHA identifies regulatory actions for several groups of PMT / vPvM substances

During the month of April, ECHA published several assessments of regulatory needs, identifying potential PMT / vPvM substances and suggesting follow-up regulatory actions:

- ▼ Assessment of regulatory needs for [Primary diaminobenzenes and derivatives](#): identifies nine substances with potential PMT/vPvM hazard, proposes compliance checks and CLH to clarify PMT/vPvM hazard and suggests potential restrictions of certain professional uses in cosmetics, coatings, adhesives, and polymer production if hazard confirmed.
- ▼ Assessment of regulatory needs for [Amine-Terminated Aliphatic Ethers](#): identifies seven substances with potential PMT/vPvM hazard, proposes compliance checks and CLH to clarify PMT/vPvM hazard and suggests potential restriction of some professional uses where there is high release

potential into the environment from use in adhesives, sealants, paints, coatings and cleaning products if hazard confirmed.

- ▼ [Assessment of regulatory needs for tall oils](#): identifies potential PMT / vPvM hazard for eight substances and proposes to carry out first compliance checks, which may be followed by CLH to confirm the PMT/vPvM hazard.
- ▼ [Assessment of regulatory needs for Phenyl-terminated non-linear alcohols and their aliphatic esters](#): proposes compliance checks for three substances to generate data clarifying PMT/vPvM hazards, which may be followed by CLH.

Poland launches legal challenge against UWWTD's EPR system before CJEU

The Polish government brought [action before the Court of Justice of the European Union](#) on 10 March 2025 (details published on 22 April) against Article 9 of the revised Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive introducing an extended producer responsibility scheme in which producers of pharmaceuticals and cosmetics would contribute a minimum of 80% of the costs of quaternary treatment. Poland calls for the annulment of the provision based on the claim that the EPR scheme introduced by the Directive is in breach of the polluter pays principle and the principle of equal treatment as it places the responsibility solely on the pharmaceutical and cosmetics industry 'while ignoring other categories of producers which contribute to the emission of those pollutants'. According to the applicant, the EPR scheme also breaches the proportionality principle 'by establishing measures which incur costs that are disproportionate to the attainment of the objectives pursued'. This legal action follows similar complaints brought before the Court by the cosmetics and pharmaceutical industry in March, which presented similar arguments to those of Poland to call for an amendment of the EPR scheme.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to provide feedback to the [Call for evidence](#) and respond to the [public consultation](#) on the evaluation of the Good Laboratory Practices Directives: **6 June 2025**.
- ▼ Deadline to respond to the [public consultation](#) on the evaluation of the Cosmetic Products Regulation: **28 July 2025**.

6 Regulatory watch – June 2025

European Water Resilience Strategy contains limited actions on water pollution

The European Commission published the [European Water Resilience Strategy](#) on 4 June 2025. The Strategy sets an overall water efficiency goal of ‘enhancing water efficiency by at least 10% by 2030’ by reducing demand, over-abstraction and improving efficiency across sectors. The Strategy however leaves the development of a methodology to set water efficiency targets to future work with Member States and stakeholders and the establishment of common targets to the review of the strategy in 2027.

Regarding water pollution, the Strategy recognises that ‘Water quality and quantity are two sides of the same coin’ and that Europe ‘must continue working on preventing pollution at source’. It also states that ‘urgent action is needed to tackle pollutants which pose a risk to our vital sources of drinking water’ including highly persistent pollutants such as PFAS and claims that ‘the EU must take decisive efforts to clean up sites already strongly polluted by these, and other, ubiquitous, persistent, bio-accumulative and toxic substances’. In terms of planned actions, the main initiatives listed in the Strategy concern increasing efforts to better implement EU water legislation in the Member States and funding for remediation. The Commission announces the establishment of a ‘public-private initiative to achieve a technological breakthrough in feasible and affordable methods for the detection and remediation of PFAS and other persistent chemicals’, with the caution that the right financial partners must be found first to launch the initiative. Regarding funding, the Strategy also announces further cooperation between the Commission and the European Investment Bank to deploy water investments.

The Strategy also makes references to the extended producer responsibility system under the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive, against which legal actions have been taken by the cosmetic and pharmaceutical industries and announces that ‘the Commission will conduct an updated study of costs and its potential impacts on concerned sectors’.

Soil Monitoring Directive establishes requirements to monitor PFAS, pesticides and their metabolites and a common approach to the identification and management of contaminated sites

On 10 April, the Council and the Parliament reached a [provisional agreement on the Soil Monitoring Directive](#), which has now been made public. The provisional agreement is currently undergoing formal approval by both institutions. The ENVI Committee of the European Parliament has voted in favour of the text on 4 June. The Council should hold a formal vote on the text after the summer.

The Directive establishes the first EU-wide framework requiring Member States to monitor and assess soil health using common descriptors. To gather data on soil contamination, Member States are required to establish a list of soil contaminants including pesticides, their metabolites and PFAS. The Commission is also mandated to adopt, within 18 months of the Directive’s entry into force, an indicative list of high-risk contaminants, including PFAS and pesticides, for which further data is needed. Member States will monitor the selected PFAS (PFAS-21, PFAS-43, or their own selection in

their national list) and selected pesticides and metabolites, although, to limit the monitoring costs, Member States are allowed to perform measurements only on a limited number of sampling points.

Regarding contaminated sites, the final agreement remains relatively close to the original Commission proposal, although with longer deadlines provided to Member States. Member States must identify all potentially contaminated sites within 10 years of the Directive's entry into force (instead of 7 years in the Commission's proposal). As proposed by the Council during negotiations, only sites existing at or before that date are included. Potentially contaminated sites then undergo soil investigations to confirm contamination, and if contamination is confirmed, site-specific risk assessments to evaluate risks to health and the environment. As in the original Commission proposal, Member States define individually what constitutes an unacceptable risk for human health and the environment. Member States are required to take appropriate risk reduction measures 'without undue delay' (no other timeline is provided in the Directive). Member States must also set up a public register of contaminated and potentially contaminated sites within four years of the Directive's entry into force.

Council mandate on the pharmaceutical package maintains main provisions on environmental risk assessments of medicinal products

The Council adopted its [mandate for negotiations](#) with the European Parliament on the pharmaceutical legislative package, consisting of a Directive and a Regulation, on 4 June 2025. The Council maintained the main provisions from the Commission proposal on environmental risk assessments of medicinal products, including the proposal that the ERA must indicate whether the pharmaceutical product contains PBT, vPvB, PMT, vPvM, or endocrine disruptor. The Council also retained that the incompleteness of the ERA or deficiencies in addressing environmental risks is a ground for refusing the marketing authorisation of a medicinal product. However, the Council added a caveat that such deficiencies would not justify a refusal of the market authorisation if 'these deficiencies are justified by the applicant and either post-authorisation environmental risk assessment studies can be requested, or the identified risks can be mitigated with appropriate risk mitigation measures'. Finally, the Council also maintained the provision subjecting to medical prescription medicinal products containing active substances that are PBT, vPvB, PMT or vPvM (where medical prescription is required as an environmental risk minimisation measure and unless other circumstances of use justify otherwise).

The Parliament had adopted its resolution on the package in April 2024, in which MEPs had also kept without significant changes provisions from the Commission's proposal on environmental risk assessment of medicinal products and medical prescription for products containing PBT, vPvB, PMT or vPvM active substances. There should therefore be a broad consensus on these provisions during upcoming interinstitutional negotiations.

ECHA launches consultation on classification of TFA and sodium trifluoroacetate as PMT and vPvM

ECHA has published the two CLH dossiers prepared by the German authorities to revise the harmonised classification of [trifluoroacetic acid](#) (TFA) and adopt a new harmonised classification for [sodium trifluoroacetate and other inorganic salts of trifluoroacetic acid](#). New proposed hazards include PMT, vPvM and Reprotoxic 1B. The public consultations on the two dossiers are open until **27 July 2025**.

German authorities also submitted to ECHA a CLH dossier to revise the harmonised classification of benzotriazole; sodium 1H-benzotriazolide; potassium 1H-benzotriazolide; and other inorganic salts. New proposed hazards include PMT, vPvM, endocrine disruptor for environment 1, carcinogen 1 and reprotoxic 2. ECHA is running the accordance check on the dossier.

Third workshop on the Roadmap to phase out animal testing on 16-17 June will be livestreamed

The Commission and ECHA jointly organise a third workshop to discuss elements of the roadmap to phase out animal testing for chemical safety assessments on 16-17 June. The workshop will be livestreamed from [ECHA's website](#) and [ECHA's youtube channel](#) (registration in Helsinki is closed). The purpose of the workshop is to present proposed recommendations of the roadmap for stakeholder consultation.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to contribute to the public consultations on the classification of [trifluoroacetic acid](#) and [sodium trifluoroacetate and other inorganic salts of trifluoroacetic acid](#): **25 July 2025**.
- ▼ Deadline to respond to the [public consultation](#) on the evaluation of the Cosmetic Products Regulation: **28 July 2025**.

7 Regulatory watch – July 2025

Provisional agreement on the common data platform includes databases on substances in articles and alternatives to substances of concern

The Council and the European Parliament reached a [provisional agreement](#) on the One Substance One Assessment package on 12 June 2025. The Package contains a Regulation establishing a common data platform on chemicals and a Regulation and Directive amending several existing legal acts with the aim of streamlining risk assessment tasks and improving cooperation across EU agencies. The ENVI Committee of the European Parliament voted in favour of the agreements on 3 July; they still need to be formally adopted in the Parliament's plenary and by the Council.

As set out in the Commission proposal, the common data platform will include the Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring ('IPCHEM'), a repository of reference values adopted under EU legislation, a database of study notifications, information on regulatory processes, information on obligations under Union chemicals legislation; a repository of standard formats and controlled vocabularies, a database on environmental sustainability-related data. In addition to these data services, the agreement on the common data platform maintained the proposal from the Parliament to include in the platform a database of information on substances in articles and a database of information on alternatives to substances of concern.

The Regulation tasks the EEA and ECHA with the creation of a framework of indicators to monitor chemical pollution throughout a chemical's lifecycle (emissions, occurrence and fate) and the drivers and impacts of exposure to chemicals. Indicators should also measure the effectiveness of chemicals legislation and the transition towards the production of safe and sustainable chemicals. The framework will include, to the extent possible, 'an aggregated territory-based risk indicator' to monitor time and spatial trends in exposure of populations to chemicals and associated health risks. The framework of indicators will be accessible in the form of an indicator dashboard made available through the common data platform. The Regulation also tasks ECHA and EFSA, in cooperation with the EEA, to commission an EU-wide human biomonitoring study covering all Member States 4 years after entry into force of the Regulation. No regular EU-wide biomonitoring study (as was proposed by the Parliament) is however required in the final agreement.

The Regulation tasks the EEA to establish an early warning system for emerging chemical risks, within one year of the entry into force of the Regulation, aggregating signals from various sources (including data from EU agencies and national early warning systems). While the final agreement maintained the possibility for ECHA to commission scientific studies to investigate further emerging chemical risks identified through the early warning system, other amendments from the Parliament related to follow-up actions from authorities were not included in the final agreement.

Amendments from the Council limiting the scope of data on medicinal products to be included in the platform were maintained in the final agreement. The Commission will carry out an assessment to analyse whether other chemicals data related to medicinal

products should be included in the platform in the future. Legacy data from the European Medical Agency (data submitted before the entry into force of the regulation) will be gradually integrated into the platform, starting six years after the regulation enters into force.

The common data platform will be created and operated by ECHA, within three years from the entry into force of the Regulation (likely end of 2028), with the exception of the database on environmental sustainability related data, to be established six years after the date of entry into force of the Regulation.

Provisional agreement on Toys regulation bans the intentional use of PFAS in toys

On 10 April, the Council and the European Parliament reached a [provisional agreement on the Toy Safety Regulation](#), which was made public on 11 June. The agreement maintained the proposal from the European Parliament to prohibit the intentional use of PFAS (defined according to the OECD definition) in toys, components of toys or micro-structurally distinct parts of toys. The prohibition does not apply to batteries in toys and toy components necessary for electronic or electric functions of the toy if the substance is full inaccessible. As initially proposed by the Commission, generic prohibitions based on CLP classification, which already existed for CMRs in the previous Toys Directive, are extended to endocrine disruptors for human health category 1 or 2; substances toxic to a specific target organ category 1 (single or repeated exposure), respiratory sensitisers category 1, to which were added in the final text skin sensitisers 1A. Proposals from the Parliament to add to this list endocrine disruptors for the environment, PMT/vPvM and PBT/vPvB were not maintained in the final agreement. Exemptions to generic prohibitions and to the PFAS prohibition may be granted by the Commission following safety and alternative assessments by ECHA. The Regulation will apply 54 months after the entry into force of the Regulation (Q1 2030 if the Regulation enters into force Q4 2025).

ECHA identifies regulatory actions for several groups of PMT / vPvM substances

ECHA published two assessments of regulatory needs identifying potential PMT / vPvM substances. The assessment of regulatory needs for [azohydroxynaphthoic acid pigments](#) identifies potential PMT/vPvM hazard for all 22 substances from the group and the assessment of regulatory needs for [alkoxy \(phenyl and chlorinated alkyl\) and chlorinated chloro alkyl silanes](#) identifies potential PMT / vPvM hazard for 13 substances (out of 23 in the group). In both cases, the assessment proposes CLH as first step to clarify the PMT/vPvM hazard.

European Parliament Research Service points to delays in implementation of the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability

The European Parliament Research Service (EPRS) published a '[Targeted scrutiny of the EU chemicals strategy for sustainability](#)', in which they assess the achievements of the strategy adopted in 2020. The briefing concludes that, if significant progress has been made in the implementation of the 85 actions contained in the strategy, several key actions, such as the revision of REACH, have not yet been implemented. The EPRS also concludes that efforts to manage risks from hazardous substances, and in particular

chemical mixtures and persistent substances such as PFAS, are ‘undermined by regulatory delays and fragmented implementation’.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to [provide feedback](#) on the draft Commission implementing regulation establishing the list of safeners and synergists to be included in the work programme for the gradual review of safeners and synergists that exist on the market: **8 July 2025**.
- ▼ Deadline to contribute to the public consultations on the classification of [trifluoroacetic acid](#) and [sodium trifluoroacetate and other inorganic salts of trifluoroacetic acid](#): **25 July 2025**.
- ▼ Deadline to respond to the [public consultation](#) on the evaluation of the Cosmetic Products Regulation: **28 July 2025**.
- ▼ Deadline to respond to the [public consultation](#) on EFSA’s Assessment Report on the active substance bromuconazole: **16 August 2025**.
- ▼ Deadline to respond to the [public consultation](#) on the CLH dossier of bromuconazole: **18 August 2025**.
- ▼ Deadline to provide feedback to the [call for evidence](#) and contribute to the public consultation on the evaluation of the Fertilising Products Regulation: **19 September 2025**.

8 Regulatory watch – August 2025

EU Court upheld ECHA’s decision to identify Melamine as SVHC

Following ECHA’s decision on 16 December 2022 identifying melamine as substances of very high concern (SVHC), several melamine producers from several countries (Germany, Austria, Belgium, Switzerland and the United States) had brought an action before the General Court of the European Union seeking the annulment of that decision. In two judgments published on 9 July 2025 ([Case T-163/23](#) and [Case T-167/23](#); see also General Court [press release](#)), the General Court rejected the arguments presented by the applicants and dismissed the action. In particular, the Court rejected the applicants’ argument that the mobility of melamine could not be regarded as an intrinsic property capable of having serious effects on human health or the environment which give rise to an equivalent level of concern, in the meaning of Article 57(f) of the REACH Regulation.

Commission’s Chemicals Industry Action Plan announced EU-wide PFAS monitoring framework

On 8 July 2025, the Commission published the Communication [‘A European Chemicals Industry Action Plan’](#), which contained a section on PFAS. Regarding the PFAS restriction, the Commission committed to issue proposal as soon as possible after receiving ECHA’s opinion. In the action plan, the Commission also announced ‘targeted investment and research into safe and sustainable alternatives’ and increased remediation efforts. On remediation, the Commission reiterated the announcement from the Water Resilience Strategy to ‘set up a public-private initiative to achieve a technological breakthrough in feasible and affordable methods for the detection and remediation of PFAS’. Finally, the plan indicated that ‘an EU-wide PFAS monitoring framework will be developed, to centralise information, identify pollution hotspots, highlight successful remediation practices, and collect data from relevant legislation’.

Denmark removed authorisations for 23 plant protection products containing active substances degrading into TFA

The Danish Environmental Protection Agency has decided in July 2025 to [withdraw the approval of 23 plant protection products](#) containing six active substances (fluazinam, fluopyram, diflufenican, mefentrifluconazole, tau-fluvalinate, and flonicamid) on the grounds that these six active substances degrade into TFA and leachate TFA to groundwater. Depending on the product, the ban for sale enters into force on 30 August 2025 and 31 December 2025 and the ban for use enters into force respectively on 31 December 2025 and 30 September 2026. The EPA is expected to issue a decision on ten other products containing those six active substances in August-September 2025.

Italy adopted mandatory drinking water parameters for the Sum of 4 PFAS and TFA

Italy adopted in June 2025 a [legislative decree](#) amending its transposition of the Drinking Water Directive. The decree removed the parameter ‘Total PFAS’ from the law to maintain only the parameter ‘Sum of PFAS’ from the Directive. In its previous law, Italy had extended the sum parameter to 24 PFAS; the new decree extended it to cover 30 PFAS (Sum of 20+ GenX, ADONA, 6:2 FTSA, C6O4 and six carboxylated

chloro-perfluoropolyethers used in the production of fluoropolymers ADV-N2, ADV-N3, ADV-N4, ADV-N5, ADV-M3, ADV-M4). The new decree also introduced two new binding drinking water parameters, one for the Sum of 4 PFAS (PFOA, PFNA, PFHxS, PFOS) of 20ng/L and one for TFA of 10 µg/L. Italy is the second Member States to adopt a drinking water parameter for TFA, after Denmark (9 µg/L).

Commission published proposals for ECHA's founding Regulation and chemicals omnibus regulation

On 8 July 2025, the Commission published a proposal for a [Regulation on the governance of the European Chemicals Agency](#) (currently part of the REACH Regulation). The proposal notably strengthens the capacity of RAC and SEAC (making the nomination of experts by Member States mandatory). On the same day, the Commission released the [proposal for a Regulation on the 'simplification of certain requirements and procedures for chemical products'](#) (chemicals omnibus regulation). The proposal reviews and/or postpones the implementation of some of the labelling rules adopted last year in the CLP revision (e.g. mandatory font sizes), removes requirements for extended REACH Registration of fertilizers, and simplifies the derogation process for using CMRs in cosmetics.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to provide feedback to the [call for evidence](#) and contribute to the public consultation on the evaluation of the Fertilising Products Regulation: **19 September 2025**.
- ▼ Deadline to respond to the [public consultation](#) launched by EFSA's Pesticide Peer Review Unit on the Draft statement on consumer health-based guidance values on trifluoroacetic acid (TFA): **22 September 2025**. The consultation follows the request from the European Commission to EFSA to issue an EFSA statement and review the recommended toxicological reference values, i.e. acceptable daily intake (ADI) and acute reference dose (ARfD), for TFA.

9 Regulatory watch – September 2025

Updated PFAS restriction expands derogations and transitional periods for industrial PFAS uses; eight ‘new’ sectors identified not part of the current restriction

On 20 August 2025, ECHA published the [updated PFAS restriction proposal](#), prepared by authorities from Denmark, Germany, the Netherlands, Norway and Sweden, acting as the Dossier Submitter. The update took into account the evidence gathered from the public consultation, held in 2023.

The proposed restriction, backed by dossier submitters, is still that of a ban with use-specific, time-limited derogations. The updated restriction text maintained the general transitional period of 18 months and time-limited derogations of 5 years to 12 years (in addition to the 18 months) for specific uses, based on the availability (and prospects for future availability) of alternatives. The updated restriction also acknowledged the possibility of adding a review clause, to account for uses where alternatives are not available after 12 years, without introducing it in the proposed legal text.

The updated restriction turned many of the ‘potential derogations’ listed in the initial text into actual derogations (e.g. for electronics, refrigerants) and expanded the list of derogations for certain sectors (e.g. PPE, medical devices, industrial uses such as lubricants and solvents, semiconductors, energy infrastructure). The updated restriction also introduced derogations for second-hand articles, spare parts, articles made of recovered paper and board, textile, and plastic containing PFAS above the specified concentration limits. The updated restriction also introduced time-unlimited derogations for uses under product and process orientated research and development (PPORD), and for starting materials and intermediates used in PFAS manufacturing for derogated uses. For PFAS manufacturing, the restriction sets emission limits to water, air and soil.

In a [note published on 27 August](#), ECHA indicated that the evaluation of the restriction proposal by the Committees would be completed in 2026, with the consultation on the SEAC draft opinion happening in the first half of 2026. The note also stated that the Committees’ opinions will not cover the eight new sectors identified and will be limited to the 14 sectors covered by the initial restriction dossier. These eight sectors were identified and assessed based on information provided in the public consultation and include printing; sealing; machinery; other medical applications; military applications; explosives; technical textiles; and broader industrial uses (e.g. solvents and catalysts). According to ECHA, including these new sectors would not be feasible in this timeline. The note however does not provide any details on how these eight sectors will be integrated into the restriction in the future.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to provide feedback to the [call for evidence](#) and contribute to the public consultation on the evaluation of the Fertilising Products Regulation: **19 September 2025**.
- ▼ Deadline to respond to the [public consultation](#) launched by EFSA's Pesticide Peer Review Unit on the Draft statement on consumer health-based guidance

values on trifluoroacetic acid (TFA): **22 September 2025**. The consultation follows the request from the European Commission to EFSA to issue an EFSA statement and review the recommended toxicological reference values, i.e. acceptable daily intake (ADI) and acute reference dose (ARfD), for TFA.

10 Regulatory watch – October 2025

Surface and groundwater quality standards for PFAS adopted but not to be complied with before 2039

On 23 September, Council and Parliament reached a provisional agreement on the revision of the Water Framework Directive, the Environmental Quality Standards Directive and the Groundwater Directive with regards to priority substances in surface and groundwater (after three years of legislative procedure!). According to institutions' press releases ([Parliament](#) and [Council](#)), the agreement introduces environmental quality standards (EQS) for new surface water pollutants – including for the sum of 25 PFAS (the 25th substance being TFA, not included in the original Commission proposal). Quality standards are also created for the sum of selected pesticides including glyphosate, certain pharmaceuticals (including ibuprofen and diclofenac) and Bisphenol A. Groundwater quality standards are added for PFAS, non-relevant metabolites of pesticides and certain pharmaceuticals. The timeline proposed by the Council has been maintained in the provisional agreement: Member States will have until 2039 to achieve compliance with the new standards both for surface water and groundwater, with, in addition, a possible extension until 2045 under strict conditions. The 20-year deadline for phasing out priority hazardous substances has been kept in the agreement. The agreement also includes the creation of a groundwater watchlist. Further details will be provided in the next regulatory watch when the text of the provisional agreement becomes publicly available.

Public consultation on SEAC opinion on PFAS restriction scheduled for March 2026

ECHA announced it will launch the consultation on the draft opinion of the SEAC on the PFAS restriction following the Committee's meeting in March 2026. The consultation will cover impacts of restricting the use of PFAS across various sectors and the availability and feasibility of alternatives. ECHA will organise a [webinar](#) on the consultation for potential participants on 30 October 2025.

ECHA launched Call for Evidence on substances of concern in packaging

ECHA has launched a [Call for Evidence](#) to support the preparation of a study report identifying substances of concern in packaging. The report is mandated by the Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR), which came into force on 11 February 2025. The report should also consider appropriate follow-up measures, such as restrictions of substances of concern in packaging. The Call for evidence aims to gather information on packaging materials and their use, tonnages, substances used in packaging, its manufacturing and downstream processing / recycling as well as waste management and the recycling technologies used. The Call is open until 28 October 2025.

France specifies its national reduction targets for industrial discharges of PFAS in water

The French PFAS law ([Law No. 2025-188 aiming to protect the population from the risks associated with PFAS substances](#)), adopted on 27 February 2025, required the government to adopt national targets for the gradual reduction of industrial emissions of PFAS in water, with the aim of eliminating these discharges within 5 years. In a [decree](#)

published on 8 September 2025, France specified the national targets, with a first aim to reduce water discharges of PFAS from industrial facilities by 70% by 27 February 2028, compared to the estimated or measured emissions for the year 2023. Subsequently, these discharges should be ended by 27 February 2030. The decree however does not specify the operational procedures for implementing this objective in the coming years.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to provide feedback on the [draft act](#) listing additional substances as unacceptable co-formulants in PPP in Annex III to the PPPR: **17 October 2025**.
- ▼ Deadline to provide feedback to ECHA's [call for evidence](#) on substances in packaging and packaging waste: **28 October 2025**.

11 Regulatory watch – November 2025

Council conclusions on water resilience call for tackling PFAS (including TFA) pollution at source

EU environment ministers adopted at the Environment Council on 21 October [Council conclusions on the European water resilience strategy](#), published by the Commission in June 2025. In the conclusions, ministers ‘underline the need to address and prevent water pollution at source, including excess nutrients and persistent and emerging pollutants, such as PFAS, including TFA’. They ‘urge the Commission to take the necessary measures [...] to phase out the most harmful chemicals’ and stress ‘the urgency for the Union to tackle pollutants at the source that pose a risk to our vital sources of drinking water’. The conclusions invite the Commission to ‘report on the progress of the strategy’s implementation’ and to ‘undertake a mid-term review [...] by 2027’.

Unclear timeline for legislative proposal on the revision of REACH following negative opinion on impact assessment

End of September the Commission confirmed that the impact assessment accompanying the revision of the REACH Regulation had received a negative opinion from the Regulatory Scrutiny Board, an independent body in the Commission providing quality control for the Commission’s impact assessments. Following the negative opinion, an amended impact assessment will need to be resubmitted to the Board, which will cause delays in the publication of the legislative proposal, until now planned for Q4 2025.

At the Environmental Council on 21 October, Sweden, Austria, Belgium, France, Spain, the Netherlands, Luxembourg, Lithuania, Hungary, and Slovakia [called for clarification on the timeline for the proposal](#). They also underlined that the revision should not only be a simplification exercise but a real modernisation of REACH to make the legislation more efficient and protect better human health and the environment. In its response to Member States, the Commissioner for Environment, Jessica Roswall, confirmed that the main priorities for the revision have not changed and indicated that the Commission services are ‘fully engaged’ in strengthening the impact assessment underpinning the legislative proposal, without providing a timeline for resubmitting to the Regulatory Scrutiny Board.

Denmark bans the use of 8 more PPPs containing active substances degrading into TFA

The Danish Environmental Protection Agency withdrawn in July 2025 the approval of 25 plant protection products containing six active substances (fluazinam, fluopyram, diflufenican, mefentrifluconazole, tau-fluvalinate, and flonicamid) on the grounds that these six active substances degrade into TFA and leachate TFA to groundwater. On 30 September 2025, the Agency [announced having withdrawn the approval of eight more plant protection products](#) containing those six active substances, bringing the number of banned products to 33. Deadline for possession and use of these eight products are set in December 2025, August 2026 and November 2026 depending on the product.

Updates on legislative / regulatory procedures:

- ▼ **Restriction on PFAS in firefighting foams adopted:** The [REACH restriction on PFAS in firefighting foams](#) was adopted on 3 October by the Commission and entered into force on 23 October. The restriction will take effect following transitional periods from one to ten years depending on the use.
- ▼ **Soil Monitoring Directive adopted by co-legislators:** Following the adoption of the provisional agreement on the Soil Monitoring Directive by the Council on 29 September, the European Parliament formally adopted the act in plenary on 23 October. The act is now awaiting signature before publication in the Official Journal and entry into force.
- ▼ **Provisional agreement on the revision of water legislation published:** the [text of the provisional agreement](#) reached by Council and Parliament on 23 September was published on 9 October. A full overview of the agreement is provided in the [excel sheet](#); main points are summarised below:
 - **PFAS and TFA:** a surface water quality standard is created for the sum of 25 PFAS (Sum of 24 PFAS from the original Commission proposal + TFA) - 0,0044 µg/L in water and 0,077 µg/L in biota. The groundwater parameter for the Sum of PFAS is aligned with the Drinking Water Directive (PFAS 20 0,10 µg/L) and a quality standard for the Sum of 4 PFAS is created (0,0044 µg/L). In the next review of quality standards, the Commission should consider establishing quality standards for PFAS Total and TFA (separately) in surface waters and groundwater. The Commission is also tasked with supplementing the guidance on monitoring PFAS Total to cover surface and groundwater.
 - **Pesticides:** a surface water quality standard is created for the 'Sum of active substances in pesticides' for which an EQS is set in the Directive (0.2 µg/L). In the next review of quality standards, the Commission should consider the possible inclusion of a surface water quality standard for the 'Sum of selected pesticides by 'mode of action''. A new groundwater quality standard is created for non-relevant metabolite of pesticides. Within two years of the entry into force of the Directive, the Commission must adopt a list of known pesticide metabolites indicating which are relevant and non-relevant (and update it every 6 years). In the next review of groundwater quality standards, the Commission should consider whether to revise the quality standards pesticides (individual and total) and for non-relevant metabolites.
 - **Pharmaceuticals:** At the next review of the surface and groundwater quality standards, the Commission should consider the introduction of a quality standard for the 'sum of selected pharmaceuticals by mode of action' in surface and groundwater.
 - **Application and review of quality standards:** new quality standards will take effect from 22 December 2027, with the aim of achieving good surface water chemical status in relation to those substances by 22 December 2039. The Commission is

tasked with reviewing the surface and groundwater quality standards every six years and, where appropriate, to issue a legislative proposal for the revision of the standards. ECHA is tasked to prepare scientific reports to support the review, including proposals for quality standards or threshold values and analytical methods.

- **Surface and groundwater watchlists:** the surface and groundwater watchlists have to be established two years after the entry into force of the Directive and then updated every three years. The groundwater watchlist is capped to five substances, the surface water watchlist to ten substances. Member States have to monitor each substance on the watchlists over a 24-month period. ECHA is tasked to prepare scientific reports to support the review of the watchlists, which will contain a list of candidate substances and indicative analysis methods and maximum acceptable limits of quantification for each substance.
- **Joint monitoring facility:** the agreement tasks the Commission with publishing within 18 months of the entry into force of the Directive a report on options for the establishment, financing and functioning of a joint European monitoring facility and if appropriate, to put forward a legislative proposal in order to establish it.
- **Extended producer responsibility:** the agreement tasks the Commission to publish a report within three years on the possibility to include an extended producer responsibility mechanism in the Water Framework Directive. The report should evaluate the feasibility of requiring producers that place on the EU market products containing any of the substances that have an EQS or a groundwater quality standard to contribute to the costs of monitoring programmes.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to provide [feedback](#) the proposed founding regulation for ECHA: **2 December 2025**.

12 Regulatory watch – December 2025

Environmental Omnibus weakens and delays implementation of the Industrial Emissions Directive

On 10 December, the European Commission published a [package of proposals for the simplification of administrative burdens in environmental legislation](#) (eighth ‘Omnibus’). The proposals amend a large number of legal acts on waste, industrial emissions and environmental assessments. Proposed measures aim to accelerate environmental assessments in permitting procedures and simplify reporting and environmental management requirements. The proposals include (non-exhaustive list):

- ▼ **Reduced requirements for environmental management system (‘EMS’) under the Industrial Emissions Directive:** the revised IED had introduced a requirement for operators of industrial installations to establish an EMS for each installation. The Omnibus postpones the deadline to implement the EMS from 2027 to 2030 and proposes that industrial installations managed by the same company in one Member State can be covered by the same EMS. The Omnibus also repeals the requirement to include in the EMS a chemical inventory of the hazardous substances present in or emitted from the installation, a chemical risks assessment of the impact of these substances on human health and the environment and an analysis of the possibilities for substituting them with safer alternatives or reducing their use or emissions. Deleting this requirement means weakening the links between the IED and REACH that had been created by the revision in 2024 as the chemical inventory was meant to give ‘special regard’ to SVHCs and substances restricted under REACH. Although the EMS did not have to set reduction targets for hazardous substances, it was a first step towards emission reduction that is now removed.
- ▼ **Transitional periods for the application of certain new IED requirements:** the Omnibus proposes to postpone the application of certain new IED requirements beyond July 2026 to give operators and authorities more time to comply. This concerns, among others, the requirements for Member States to ensure that permits include emission limit values for polluting substances listed in Annex II IEPR and an obligation to assess the need to prevent or reduce emissions of hazardous substances (Art. 14(1)(a) and (ab)); or higher monitoring frequencies in groundwater and soil (Art. 16(2)). Their application will be phased in from July 2026 and will become applicable at the latest on 1 September 2036.
- ▼ **Removal of the SCIP notification:** since January 2021, the Waste Framework Directive required suppliers of articles to notify SVHCs in articles to ECHA for inclusion in the SCIP database. The SCIP database aimed to help waste operators and recyclers to better handle products containing hazardous substances. The database had attracted criticisms on its little usefulness for waste management and recycling because of issues related to data quality and usability. Although there is not yet a replacement for the SCIP database, solutions may exist. The requirement for supplier to provide data on SVHCs in articles could be picked up in ESPR delegated acts for specific product groups, which would lead to the inclusion of the data in the Digital Product Passport. Although this could be a better solution for waste operators and consumers, it

will still depend on implementation (e.g. level of data aggregation). According to the recently adopted Regulation establishing a common data platform on chemicals, the platform will also include a database of substances of concern in articles, which may replace the SCIP database.

- ▼ **Clarification of the labelling of hazardous substances in batteries:** the revised Batteries Regulation requires that batteries bear a label indicating hazardous substances present in the battery, without further specification of the scope of the substances to be labelled. The Omnibus clarifies that 1) substances on the Candidate List and 2) substances fulfilling SVHC criteria and listed in Annex VI of CLP have to be labelled, if they are present in the battery in a concentration equal or above 0.1% w/w.

The [Communication](#) accompanying the legislative proposals also lists future simplification measures to be expected in the coming year and announces a general ambition to ‘stress-test’ ‘the full set of environmental acquis during the 2024-2029 mandate of the Commission’. The Communication reiterates the Commission’s intention to revise the Water Framework Directive in 2026 with a focus on simplification. Regarding the Packaging and Packaging waste Regulation, the Commission will issue a guidance on common issues raised by industry including testing for PFAS in food packaging. The Communication also announces that the Circular Economy Act, expected in Q3 2026 may include ‘larger scale reform of extended producer responsibility scheme’. While it does mention the revision of REACH as a future simplification measures, the Communication does not provide further indications on timeline or content.

Commission announces revision of Water Framework Directive by Q2 2026

The European Commission adopted on 3rd December the [RESourceEU Action Plan](#) to accelerate efforts to secure the EU's supply of critical raw materials. The Action Plan announces that ‘by Q2 2026 the Commission will review and revise the Water Framework Directive [...] paying particular attention to simplification and the need to address potential bottlenecks, in order to promote circularity and access to critical raw materials in the EU, while protecting the environment and human health’. The exact content of this revision is not further detailed in the Action Plan. According to the Action Plan, the Commission will also, by Q1 2026, issue a guidance document ‘to enable a simpler and more harmonised implementation in Member States of the EU law on environmental permitting, including aspects relating to the mining sector’. This guidance will cover the Water Framework Directive, including compliance with Environmental Quality Standards at the level of the water body.

In addition, the Action Plan indicates that the ‘Commission will [...] consider the specific operational realities of the extractive, recycling and processing sectors in the announced revision of REACH and possible future revisions of the Carcinogens, Mutagens and Reprotoxic Substances (CMRD) Directive’.

One substance one assessment package adopted by Council and Parliament – what are the next steps for the common data platform on chemicals in 2026?

Following the adoption of the ‘one substance, one assessment package’ by the European Parliament on 21 October, the Council adopted it on 13 November. The act is now awaiting signature before publication in the Official Journal (likely before the end of the year) and entry into force (20 days after publication).

The package includes a Regulation establishing a common data platform on chemicals. As a first step for the creation of the platform, the Commission must set up a steering committee responsible for advising on the development of the platform governance framework. This steering committee will consist of at least one representative from each of the EU Agencies and representatives of the Commission. The Commission must also adopt within 6 months of the entry into force of the Regulation an implementation plan identifying datasets of chemicals data to be included in the common data platform, together with a timeline for their inclusion. These elements – steering committee, implementation plan, governance framework – will be adopted through implementing acts. The publication of the draft implementing acts together with the one-month consultation are currently planned for Q1 2026 regarding the [setting up of the steering committee](#) and Q2 2026 (likely June 2026) regarding the [implementation plan and governance framework](#).

In addition, the Regulation tasks ECHA to establish an observatory for specific chemicals contributing to emerging chemical risks, which will replace the current EU Observatory for Nanomaterials. To do so, ECHA will publish a list of chemicals selected for scrutiny, which is expected around June 2026. The [draft implementing act and the one-month consultation](#) are currently planned for Q2 2026.

Finally, from the entry into force of the Regulation (expected early January 2026), research consortia funded by EU programmes must make available data they collect or generate to EU Agencies who will host the data: 1) human biomonitoring data to the EEA, 2) environmental sustainability related data on chemicals or materials (including data on emissions and by-products) to ECHA.

ECHA recommends inclusion of melamine in the Authorisation List

On 18 November, ECHA [recommended](#) the inclusion of melamine to the REACH Authorisation List, along with three other substances. The final decision whether or not to include the substance in Annex XIV to REACH will be taken by the Commission.

Uses of melamine as intermediate (e.g. in the production of resins/polymers or melamine salts), which account for 95 % of the total tonnage manufactured/imported in the EU, fall outside the scope of the authorisation regime. Nonetheless, ECHA estimated that the volume in the scope of authorisation is in the range 1,000 -> 10,000 t/y. ECHA [noted](#) ‘potential challenges’ with the workload that applications for authorisation for uses in scope could generate, and will therefore suggest the Commission and Member States, when transmitting its recommendation, to ‘consider whether additional or alternative regulatory risk management measures could be used to most effectively address the risks of melamine and provide the incentive for substitution’.

The recommendation follows the judgement from the Court of Justice upholding the identification of melamine as SVHC in July 2025. The ongoing appeal lodged by one of the companies was [not considered by ECHA](#) ‘legitimate grounds’ for delaying the recommendation. ECHA also clarified that the ongoing CLH process for classification of melamine as PMT/vPvM substance is completely independent from the recommendation for inclusion in Annex XIV and is not a reason to delay the recommendation.

Sweden and Norway to reevaluate authorisations of pesticides degrading into TFA

On 20 November, the Swedish Chemicals Agency has [announced](#) the re-evaluation of the authorisations of 38 plant protection products on the Swedish market containing six active substances degrading into TFA: diflufenican, flonicamid, fluazinam, fluopyram, mefentrifluconazole and tau-fluvalinate. One day later, the Norwegian Food Safety Authority [announced](#) it will also re-evaluate the authorisations of 13 plant protection products containing active substances degrading into TFA on the Norwegian market. Both authorities are initiating the reassessment with the aim to take a decision by 30 April 2028.

These reassessments follow the withdrawal of plant protection products containing those six active substances in Denmark this summer. Other Member States belonging to the Northern zone (Estonia, Finland, Iceland, Latvia, Lithuania, Norway and Sweden) shall, according to the Plant Protection Products Regulation, ‘withdraw or amend the authorisation accordingly taking into account national conditions and risk mitigation measures’ (Art. 44(4) PPPR).

Updates on legislative / regulatory procedures:

- ▼ The legislative proposal for the revision of **REACH** is now expected ‘early 2026’, [according to Eric Mamer](#), director-general for the environment at the European Commission.
- ▼ The **Soil Monitoring Directive** has been [published](#) in the Official Journal on 26 November and will enter into force on 16 December 2025. Member States must transpose the Directive in their national law by 17 December 2028.
- ▼ After its adoption by the Council on 13 October, the **Toys Regulation** was adopted in plenary by the European Parliament on 25 November. The act is awaiting signature and publication in the Official Journal.

Upcoming consultation deadlines:

- ▼ Deadline to contribute to ECHA’s [Call for evidence](#) to identify substances of concern in batteries, including substances that hamper recycling of end-of-life batteries: **10 December 2025**.

H2020 project Zero pollution of Persistent, Mobile substances
EU Grant Agreement No. 101036756